

TOWARDS THE MULTIMODAL DETECTION OF SLEEP IN PILOTS

Hicham Atassi, Dariia Averkova, Bohdan Blaha, Jan Ciganek and Tomas Kopriva

Honeywell Aerospace, Advanced Technology Europe, Brno, Czech Republic

Email: {Hicham.Atassi, Dariia.Averkova, Bohdan.Blaha, Jan.Ciganek, Tomas.Kopriva}@Honeywell.com

KEYWORDS: Sleep, pilot, detection, classification, spontaneous data, biosensing, multimodal, feature, decision tree

ABSTRACT:

The paper presents activities performed in the frame of project Clean Sky II DECK in Large Passenger Aircraft Platform 3 and related to the detection of sleep by processing the multimodal data acquired from subjects using various kinds of sensors. The data acquisition was carried out in a cockpit simulator, with each subject participating in two sessions, resulting in more than 40 hours of recorded data. The polysomnography (PSG) data were scored online by a medical expert according to the guidelines of the American Academy of Sleep Medicine (AASM). Several feature extraction and selection techniques were employed to identify the most relevant characteristics for discriminating between sleep and alert states in aviation context. The experimental results suggest that the proposed data-driven paradigm for sleep detection achieves high accuracy and shows high robustness when combining the most discriminative features extracted from the considered modalities.

1. INTRODUCTION

In May 2010 Air India's plane crash in Mangalore, India killed 158 people and left only 8 survivors [1]. The investigation revealed that the captain was asleep for more than half of the three-hour flight from Dubai. The plane was reported to have approached the airport at the wrong height and angle. After a late touchdown, the pilots attempted to take off again, but the length of the runway remaining did not allow to do so. As a result, the plane plunged off the runway into the jungle below and immediately caught fire. When the captain was trying to land the aircraft, he was said to be disoriented due to the sleep inertia. Even when controlled rest in the cockpit is allowed by the airline, there are regulations regarding the length of sleep and the minimum time to be awake before any high workload situation. Pilots on this flight clearly did not comply with them. And this is not the only such occurrence.

In a survey of 6000 pilots, conducted by ECA between 2010-2012, over 50% of pilot reported that

fatigue was impairing their ability to perform well on flight duty. [2]. Figure 1 illustrates the reported percentage of unintended sleep from fatigue across 8 European countries.

Figure 1. Percentage of the surveyed pilots dozing off and/ or experiencing micro sleeps in the cockpit.

In another study conducted in 2013-2014 in Brazil, 57.8% of 1,235 pilots affiliated to Brazilian Association of Civil Aviation Pilots (ABRAPAC) reported unintentionally falling asleep while flying the airplane [3].

The psychophysiological state of fatigue leads to partial pilot incapacitation by increasing the potential for errors, impairing judgement and psychomotor performance; sleep state represents full incapacitation, when a pilot is no longer aware of nor controlling the aircraft.

As fatigue was cited more frequently as a contributing factor to aviation accidents and incidents, the concept of Fatigue Risk Management System (FRMS) was introduced in 2008 by ICAO. According to [4], FRMS has been defined as "a data-driven means of continuously monitoring and maintaining fatigue related safety risks, based upon scientific principles and knowledge as well as operational experience that aims to ensure relevant personnel are performing at adequate levels of alertness".

FRMSs go further than simply applying the Flight Time Limitations scheme. Often, they use biomathematical models. Based on the understanding of the factors that contribute to fatigue, these models give a prognosis of fatigue

risk levels, performance levels, and/or sleep times as well as the need for rest of operators [5]. The predictions are done through sets of equations that calculate probabilities of certain events/states based on the general knowledge regarding human neurophysiology and specific person's sleep history, time working, workload, subjective evaluation of fatigue, time of day and other factors.

However, like Safety Management Systems, FRMSs rely on reporting and thus on a successful implementation of a safety culture in the organization, which in its turn depends on the individuals' perception of the importance of reporting and of potential repercussions. The refinement of biomathematical models can only be made in the iterative process, where the model is infused with the real data regarding fatigue measurements, task errors and incident data.

What contributes to the complexity is that fatigue is a dynamic state, which is not so easy to measure, model and, generalize across population. No model will be perfect at predicting the minute when a pilot falls asleep (or experiences a micro sleep).

We suggest that a real-time pilot monitoring system could be the next step in the safety management that would serve as one of the last safety barrier between an incapacitation occurrence and an accident. If sleep and drowsiness can be reliably detected by a system, then different mitigation strategies can be implemented to either prevent sleep or wake a pilot up.

A number of automotive manufacturers, such as Audi, BMW, Bosch, Ford, Subaru, Volkswagen and others, have been successfully installing driver drowsiness detection systems in the select car models. Such systems monitor driver steering pattern, lane keeping, driver face and eyes, and duration of current driving segment; they also perform certain physiological measurements. Considering that pilot tasks differ quite significantly, the same systems cannot be automatically used for pilot drowsiness and sleep detection. Pilots' interactions with avionics are very different from steering a car and are not continuous. There are no psychomotor continuous inputs to measure when the autopilot is often engaged, especially in the cruise phase when the onset of drowsiness and sleep are most likely to occur. A pilot does not need to constantly look out of the window in an attempt to monitor surrounding traffic, he or she can have their eyes off the instruments too, while consulting a non-integrated device, a manual, a check-list or even a personal phone. Pilots are even allowed to take turns napping in the cockpit if the controlled rest in cockpit operations are adopted by the airline. Therefore, a pilot closing their eyes or leaving the

seat to go to the restroom should not necessarily trigger an alert.

During the past decade, passenger demand for air traffic has been growing and is predicted to continue to do so [6]. With this trend there is also a growing global pilot shortage [7] and with it the pressure on current pilots to stay in service for longer and possibly for more hours within those years. This is one of the factors that makes fatigue and sleep detection and management initiatives in aviation so topical in the years to come.

The present article describes the approach to designing a system for the sleep detection in pilots that accommodates the specificity of their tasks and environment. This system is being designed under the Pilot State Monitoring (PSM), a Honeywell project. It grew out of the Clean Sky cooperation with partners, known as DECK (Disruptive European Cockpit) that was initiated in 2016. PSM has since been focusing on the development of a broader technology, based on non-intrusive sensing and advanced processing, that would be capable of detecting certain states that impair pilot's performance, such as sleep, drowsiness, fatigue and potentially other states.

2. SLEEP

Sleep can be defined as a state of decreased brain arousal, reduced responsiveness to the surroundings, reduced motor activity and reduced metabolism, which is naturally recurring and rapidly reversible.

It is regulated by two opposing mechanisms: the homeostatic drive for sleep and the circadian system that regulates wakefulness [8]. The two mechanisms interact. The homeostatic process ensures that a person's drive for sleep will be steadily increasing the longer he/she has been awake. This creates a neurobiological need for sleep or sleep pressure.

The circadian biological clock is regulated by its pacemaker that is located in the Suprachiasmatic Nucleus (SCN) in hypothalamus that is responsive to light and dark signals. Melatonin, a hormone responsible for the onset of sleep, is released when the eyes signal to the SCN that it is dark. Melatonin levels rise in the evening (when the light starts fading) and stay elevated during the night. In the morning, being exposed to the light, SCN commands the body to delay the production of melatonin, release cortisol instead and raise body temperature.

Other factors influence sleep too by either increasing the sleep pressure or by keeping a person awake: secretion of other hormones, such as serotonin and adenosine, sleep deprivation,

consumption of caffeine and other stimulants. Thus, circadian clock gets disrupted by departing from natural sleep pattern: keeping long irregular hours, changing time zones. The change in time and light cues forces the body to alter its normal pattern, which might have a negative impact on a person's mood, cognitive and motor performance [9].

Sleep is not a uniform state and based on the differences in the brain activity it can be divided into rapid eye movement (REM) and non-REM stages [8]. In non-REM (NREM) several more stages can be differentiated: N1, N2 and N3. During a full night's sleep, a person without sleep disorders normally goes through several sleep cycles, each of them consisting of NREM and REM sleep, usually starting with NREM. One sleep cycle on average lasts for approximately 90 minutes and typically goes through all the stages starting with N1, then progressing to N2 and N3 and going back to N2 before the REM stage (may be subject to individual differences). Most of N3 (slow-wave) occurs during the first half of the night and most of the REM sleep – during the second half.

However, it appears that such factors as the environment, age, medications taken, sleep timing and sleep deprivation change the typical sleep architecture (progression through the stages and time spent in each) [10]. For example, day sleep usually shifts most of the REM stages to the first part of the sleep period and the N3 – to the second. Or in case of sleep deprivation, there seems to be a preference for the brain to make up for the loss of the slow-wave sleep first and REM sleep after. Thus, REM stages can be pushed to either later in the sleep episode or even into the next sleep.

Polysomnography (PSG) is used as the gold standard for registering and analysing sleep. It usually consists of recording electrical activity occurring at the surface of the brain with the help of electroencephalogram (EEG), blood oxygen level, heart activity and breathing, as well as eye movements and muscle activity.

The brain activity appears on the screen as waveforms of varying frequency and amplitude, shape, continuity, synchrony, symmetry and reactivity coming from several different channels (locations on the brain surface) [11]. EEG waveform frequency bandwidths, or bands, are expressed in Table 1.

Table 1. EEG waveform frequency bandwidths

Wave	Frequency range (Hz)	Description
Delta	0 to 3.99	typical for deep sleep (N3 stage), as described below
Theta	4 to 7.99	typical for N1, N2 stages of

		sleep
Alpha	8 to 13	most present when awake with eyes closed or during REM sleep
Beta	Over 13	usually present during wakefulness

Different states (e.g. wakefulness, drowsiness, sleep) exhibit different predominant frequencies, therefore appropriate frequency analysis is crucial for the state detection when using EEG.

3. DATA COLLECTION

The data collection protocol below, and the results presented in this paper show the latest data collection campaign. As previously mentioned, the project started in 2016 and employed a series of experiments and studies, differing in the set up and objectives. This paper focus on the latest experiment conducted in the frame of Clean Sky II project DECK in Large Passenger Aircraft Platform 3.

Subjects were invited to participate in two data collection sessions that were held in a laboratory setting in a fixed base part-task cockpit simulator representative of a twin-engine glass cockpit based on an Airbus A320 shell and Falcon F900 avionics. A cruise phase of flight during night was simulated. The familiarity with the cockpit environment or aviation background were not prerequisites for participation. Participants were instructed on how to perform the actions that would be required of them during the sessions.

Session 1 and session 2 differed in length and objectives based on the following assumption: a subject will show more signs of drowsiness and is more likely to fall asleep/experience micro-sleep if his/her sleeping time is minimized on the day of the experiment (to up to 4 hours) and he/she does not take any stimulants, such as caffeine the night before and the morning of the experiment until the experiment is over.

The subject was asked to fill out the questionnaire containing biographical data questions as well as those related to their sleep. Then they were asked to perform the NPI (Neurobiological Performance Indicator) test and indicate their sleepiness on a 9-point KSS (Karolinska Sleepiness Scale [12]. Figure 2 shows a study subject in the laboratory setting with all the sensors deployed.

The subject was asked to be sufficiently rested on the day of his/her Session 1, which lasted for 1h 30min. It consisted of approximately 20 minutes of simulated ATC instructions to which subjects had to respond by providing the information requested or interacting with the avionics. ATC instructions phase was then followed by free activity (the subject

could interact with the simulator, use his/ her phone, sit still, take a nap) and approximately 10 minutes of interaction with an experimenter acting as a co-pilot.

For Session 2 the subject was asked to restrict his/ her sleep to 4 hours at most. The session lasted for 2h 30min. It consisted of 10 min of ATC instructions followed by free activity and approximately 10 minutes of co-pilot interaction (as explained above). Participants were instructed that during the free activity they could also close their eyes or sleep. Figure 3 summarises both sessions.

Figure 2. A participant at the end of a session.

Figure 3. The temporal set up of the data collection.

The main objective of Session 2 is to create the environment that would be conducive to drowsiness and sleep to collect subject's physiological and behavioural signals. Excessive interactions with the subject or asking her/him to execute certain actions over a long period of time could result in the unwanted level of arousal. The length of ATC

instructions was reduced to avoid overstimulating the subject, which could delay or prevent the onset of sleep.

The statistics and figures provided in Table 2 are based on the current number of subjects. The study is still ongoing, the results reported in the next sections are based on the amount of data processed that differs for each modality. The outcomes will be modified accordingly at the end of the data collection campaign.

Table 2. Data collection summary.

Total number of sessions	30
Sessions 1	16
Sessions 2	14
Gender distribution (M/F)	13/5
Average age	34±8
Average session 1 length	88±9 min
Average session 2 length	143±5 min
Total time of sleep data	495 min
Total time of non-sleep data	3322 min

During the sessions a sleep expert was scoring the data from the PSG device in real-time, labelling awake and sleep stages (see Fig. 4) and thus creating a hypnogram – a graph that shows the progression of sleep in time and sleep stages.

The scoring was done according to the American Academy of Sleep Medicine (AASM) guidelines [13]. AASM is a recognised expert organisation in PSG evaluation and its manual for the scoring of sleep is widely used by the sleep specialists. It advises practitioners on how to recognise each sleep stage. Sleep is scored in 30-second periods that are called epochs. A sleep expert assigns a sleep stage to each epoch. If two or more stages can be recognised in a single epoch, a practitioner will assign the stage that occurs for the greater part of the epoch.

According to the AASM manual, N1 is generally characterised by:

- Slow eye movements (SEM)
- Low-amplitude (predominantly 4-7 Hz), mixed-frequency (LAMF) EEG activity
- Alpha frequency attenuation, less than 50% Alpha activity
- Vertex sharp waves (V waves) - sharply contoured waves with duration <0.5 seconds

N2 can be generally characterised by:

- K complexes - well delineated negative sharp waves with total duration ≥0.5 seconds
- Sleep spindles - a train of distinct sinusoidal waves with frequency 11–16 Hz (most commonly 12–14 Hz) with a duration ≥0.5 seconds

- No eye movement

N3, known as deep sleep, can be generally recognised by the presence of slow wave activity (SWA) 0.5-2 Hz and receding of K complexes and spindles.

REM sleep is characterised by:

- Rapid eye movements
- Low chin muscle tone
- Sawtooth waves - A train of distinct sinusoidal waves with frequency 11–16 Hz (most commonly 12–14 Hz) with a duration ≥ 0.5 seconds, preceding a burst of rapid eye movements.

Figure 4. A sample PSG output labelled by a sleep expert. W – awake, 1 – N1 stage.

4. SLEEP DETECTION

In order to validate the performance of the designed algorithms for the parametrization of the modalities under examination, a classification experiment was performed according to the details reported in Table 3.

The experiment was performed on sleep-wise scored multimodal data of 13 participants from 20 sessions. All modalities considered for classification were acquired from the non-intrusive sensors, i.e., excluding the gold-standard PSG, which was used only for creating sleep/non-sleep ground truth. From each sensor, several cues were extracted and subsequently encoded using global features.

The features with highest discriminative power were identified using the Minimum Redundancy Maximum Relevance (MRMR) algorithm [14]. The advantages of this feature selection techniques are low computational complexity, classifier-independency and high performance in identifying uncorrelated features.

The parametrization was performed on 30-second long windows, which corresponds to the epoch length considered in the sleep scoring according to AASM. The resulting feature vectors from each modality were concatenated (feature-level fusion)

forming the final feature vector of each instance. The classification was carried out by using a boosted decision tree [15] and the performance was evaluated by a 10-fold cross validation.

Various sensor combination methods were used, usually meeting an accuracy weighted above 80% on average.

Table 3: Summary of the preliminary sleep detection experiment.

Features	Global features
Feature selection	Minimum Redundancy Maximum Relevance (MRMR) algorithm
Ground truth	The hypnogram derived from the domain expert sleep scoring according to section 8.1
Window length	30 seconds
Classifier	Boosted decision tree
Fusion	Feature-level fusion
Validation	10-fold cross validation
Corpus size	262 minutes of sleep data and 1955 minutes of non-sleep data from 20 sessions

5. CONCLUSIONS

A data collection campaign has been started and is ongoing. Participants were recruited and asked to participate in 2 experimental sessions each: session 1 was a rested condition and session 2 was a sleep-restricted session. Comparing the output from the two sessions would provide the answers regarding the differences in pilots' states. The main differences between the sessions were in rest state of the participants, the duration of the session and the amount of external stimulation at the beginning. All of these intended to increase the chance for inducing drowsiness and sleep in the session 2.

So far 30 experimental sessions have taken place: 16 of Session 1st type and 14 of Session 2nd type. The average age of participants is 34±8. In total 495 minutes of sleep data and 3322 minutes of non-sleep data have been obtained and recorded. The preliminary results are based on all the processed data available when the paper was submitted. The results will be updated once the data collection campaign is over and all the data are processed and analysed.

The whole approach, from data acquisition to signal pre-processing and parametrization was evaluated by a machine learning based experiment, performed on sleep-wise scored multimodal data of 13 participants from 20 sessions. All modalities considered for classification were acquired from the non-intrusive sensors (excluding the PSG). Despite of the small set of data considered in the experiment, sleep could be detected in most than 80% of the cases.

The main upcoming research and development activities include:

- Continuing in the data collection campaign
- Considering adding other sensors to the data collection process.
- Extending the signal parametrization portfolio by new techniques.
- Employing the classifier-level fusion with context-aware capability.
- Exhaustive research on the optimal window length for the parametrization of each modality and the following decision making.
- Exploring different classification algorithms.
- Evaluation of the proposed system in realistic environment, such as dynamic simulator or testing aircraft.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We thank Sleep Medicine Research Group at St. Anne's University Hospital Brno, Czech Republic for providing their expertise and supporting data collection campaign.

6. REFERENCES

1. Report on accident to Air India Express Boeing 737-800 aircraft VT-AXV on 22nd May 2010 at Mangalore (PDF). Government of India. Ministry of Civil Aviation. 31 October 2010.
2. Pilot Fatigue (PDF) (2012). Barometer. European Cockpit Association.
3. Marqueze, E. C., Nicola, A. C. B., Diniz, D. H., & Fischer, F. M. (2017). Working hours associated with unintentional sleep at work among airline pilots. *Revista de saude publica*, 51.
4. FRMS. Fatigue Risk Management Systems. Manual for Regulators. 1st Edition, 2012. Doc 9966. International Civil Aviation Organization.
5. Civil Aviation Safety Authority. (2014). Biomathematical fatigue models—Guidance document, CASA (Ed.) Albert Park, Australia: Dédale Asia Pacific.
6. Mazareanu, E. (2019). Annual growth in global air traffic passenger demand from 2006 to 2020. Statista. Retrieved from: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/193533/growth-of-global-air-traffic-passenger-demand/>.
7. Garcia, M. A 'Perfect Storm' Pilot Shortage Threatens Global Aviation. Forbes. Retrieved from: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/marisagarcia/2018/07/27/a-perfect-storm-pilot-shortage-threatens-global-aviation-even-private-jets/#f9fec5715492>.
8. Nicholson, A.N. (ed.). (2011) *The Neurosciences and the Practice of Aviation Medicine*. Farnham, Surrey: Ashgate.
9. Deboer, T. (2018) Sleep homeostasis and the circadian clock: Do the circadian pacemaker and the sleep homeostat influence each other's functioning? *Neurobiology of Sleep and Circadian Rhythms*, 5, 68–77.
10. Caldwell, J. A., & Caldwell, J. L. (2016). *Fatigue in aviation: A Guide to Staying Awake at the Stick* (2nd ed.). New York: Routledge.
11. Louis, E.K.S., & Frey, L.C. (2016) *Electroencephalography (EEG): An Introductory Text and Atlas of Normal and Abnormal Findings in Adults Children and Infants*, American Epilepsy Society.
12. Miley, A. Å., Kecklund, G., Åkerstedt, T. (2016). Comparing two versions of the Karolinska Sleepiness Scale (KSS). *Sleep Biological Rhythms* 14(3):257–260.
13. Berry, R.B., Brooks, R., Gamaldo, C., Harding, S.M., Lloyd, R.M., Quan, S.F., Troester, M.T., Vaughn, B.V. (2017). *AASM Scoring Manual Updates for 2017* (Version 2.4). AASM.
14. Peng, H., Long, F., & Ding, C. (2005). Feature selection based on mutual information: criteria of max-dependency, max-relevance, and min-redundancy. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis & Machine Intelligence*, (8), 1226-1238.
15. Roe, B. P., Yang, H. J., Zhu, J., Liu, Y., Stancu, I., & McGregor, G. (2005). Boosted decision trees as an alternative to artificial neural networks for particle identification. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment*, 543(2-3), 577-584.